

OSNL Open Research Software Advisory Panel Meeting

Marta Teperek | Mark van Assem | *Maria Cruz*

29 November 2024

Overview presentation

● 15:00 – 15:05 - Welcome and agenda

● 15.10 – 15.30 - Work Programme 2024 and 2025: update

● 15.30 – 15.45 – Development of the new Programme

● 15.45 - 16.55 – Community consultation discussion

● 16.55 - 17.00 - Meeting close and upcoming meetings

Quick round of introductions

Update on the Work Programme 2024 - 2025

Plans to cut OSNL budget by 50%

- We are thankful for the statements of support we have received: <https://www.openscience.nl/en/cases/budget-cuts-on-open-science-share-your-thoughts>
- All open calls and projects already awarded are 'safe'
- Activities budgeted for 2025 are currently uncertain, options to be decided by our Steering Board

Work Programme 2024-2025

Open scholarly
communication

FAIR data

Open research
software

Citizen science /
societal engagement

Programme overview

Strengthening local and thematic DCCs

- 4 institutions which were eligible to apply, didn't apply
 - The OSNL Board decided to to fund creation of DCCs at institutions which didn't yet receive funding for this
- Received good proposal with diverse approaches. The Board will decide on the 13th of December
- Observation: we might have been too restrictive on what can be applied for

Development of a new work programme 2026 - 2027

Development of work programmes in general

NPOS agenda provides overall framework

To be approved by the Steering Board & based on community consultation at various levels

A diverse array of instruments, tailored to specific topics and community needs

Considerations for the development of the new Work Programme

- There is less funding and less capacity: preference for fewer funding instruments which would be inclusive of all programme lines (and beyond)
- Considerations for Open Research Software instruments:
 - NPOS challenges not addressed in the work programme 2024 – 2025
 - Challenges not addressed by the NPOS: e.g. pertaining to open hardware, measuring the impact of research data and software
 - Challenges unlikely to be sufficiently addressed in the work programme 2024 - 2025
 - New challenges, e.g. development of open source- and FAIR data-based AI tools

Community consultation

Workshop at the Open Science Festival – co-designing the new Work Programme.

Scope: FAIR Data, Open Research Software, Open Hardware

Top challenges

Sustainability after
the end of a project
(15 votes)

Connecting existing
infrastructures
(11 votes)

Monitoring, rewarding
and measuring impact
of open science
contributions
(15 votes)

Lack of clear career paths
and recognition and
rewards for open science
professionals
(10 votes)

Maintaining Free
Open Source
Software
(7 votes)

Insufficient
capacity of open
science experts
(9 votes)

Solutions

Sustainability after
the end of a project
(15 votes)

Grants aimed at
scaling up /
adoption of outputs

Solutions

Lack of clear career paths
and recognition and
rewards for open science
professionals
(10 votes)

Job profiles (junior
↔ senior)
embedded in CLAs

Awards to celebrate
contributions of open
science professionals

Mobility programmes
and training
opportunities

Solutions

Create an overview
of infrastructures

Connecting existing
infrastructures
(11 votes)

Identify opportunities
for integration
(common protocols,
agreed standards and
formats)

Solutions

Maintaining Free
Open Source
Software (7
votes)

Traineeship/scholarship
programmes at
FOSS organisations

Reward active
contributions to
FOSS

Solutions?

Monitoring, rewarding
and measuring impact
of open science
contributions
(15 votes)

Insufficient
capacity of open
science experts
(9 votes)

Your reactions on what was shared by the community

- Are there challenges / solutions that OSNL should absolutely prioritise in the next Work Programme?
- Are there any quick wins that you see?
- Are there challenges / solutions mentioned by the community, which you think are likely to be out of scope / inappropriate to be addressed OSNL funding instruments?
- Is there anything major missing?

Break – 5min

Your reactions on what was shared by the community

- Are there challenges / solutions that OSNL should absolutely prioritise in the next Work Programme?
- Are there any quick wins that you see?
- Are there challenges / solutions mentioned by the community, which you think are likely to be out of scope / inappropriate to be addressed OSNL funding instruments?
- Is there anything major missing?

Next meetings

- Meeting in Q1/Q2 2025:
 - First ideas on how to turn community input into financial instruments
 - Work Programme 2024 and 2025 implementation update
- Meeting in Q3 2025:
 - Feedback on the draft Work Programme 2026 and 2027

Thank you!

Contact

 Marta Teperek

 m.Teperek@nwo.nl

 +31 6 10 59 03 51

 openscience.nl